

**ADDRESSING TONE-MARKING CHALLENGES IN DIGITISED YORUBA'
TEXTS FOR WEB COMMUNICATIONS**

JAPHET, Akintoye Samson

Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages

Osun State University, Osogbo

akintoye.japhet@uniosun.edu.ng | japhetakintoye@gmail.com

Tel: 08059159778 | <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3904-9103>

AWONIYI, Folorunso Emmanuel

Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages

Osun State University, Osogbo

folorunso.awoniyi@uniosun.edu.ng | Tel: 08035216039

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3595-8684>

&

ADEYEMI Aderogba

Department of Communication Studies

Osun State University, Osogbo

Email: aderogba.adeyemi@uniosun.edu.ng | Tel: 07069550894

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0357-1891>

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Abstract

This study is driven by the following questions: Do Yoruba born-digital datasets consistently observe tone orthography? What are the primary implications of neglecting tone-marking? How can tone orthography be effectively implemented in Yoruba born-digital texts? The study aims to examine the extent to which tone-marking is applied in born-digital Yoruba datasets, identify the key implications of tone-marking neglect, and explore practical strategies for ensuring the proper implementation of tone orthography in Yoruba digital texts. Utilizing the Yorùbá Web 2015 corpus (yorubawac15), data were sourced from websites such as *wikipedia.org*, *alaroyeonline.com*, *nairaland.com*, and others. A toneless search query, *aja*, was used via the Sketch Engine tool to generate a concordance, from which 50 lines were manually extracted and analyzed. The findings reveal that tone orthography is poorly implemented in the selected born-digital texts and underscore the linguistic and communicative consequences of this neglect, including ambiguity and loss of meaning. Two practical solutions are proposed: the adoption of predictive typing tools for general users and the use of Unicode keyboards for proficient writers. Due to the limited scope of the study, the analysis was confined to 50 concordance lines. This study ultimately advocates for the integration of tone orthography in Yoruba digital writing and emphasizes the importance of linguistic accuracy in the era of African digital humanities.

Keywords: African digital humanities, tone orthography, digital orthography, tone diacritics, born-digital data

Word count: 150

Introduction

One of the main problems confronting digitized texts in Yorùbá is the tone-marking orthography. Tone marking is facing a growing neglect in Yorùbá textual data which include religious publications, Yorùbá print newspapers, magazines and students' writings (Fagborun, 1989; Odejobi, 2005; Olumuyiwa, 2013). This study is focusing on the extension of such tone marking neglect in digital archives of the language (Asahiah, 2014). There is a serious concern on the poor condition of the Yorùbá born-digital textual data currently available on the web (Japhet,

Afolabi & Olatuji, 2024). The study reveals a crucial problem that can hinder the on-going digitisation projects in the language.

Born-digital data are the data that are originally codified in digital forms. They differ from analogue data. Analogue data has the following characteristics. As analogue data, audio data exist as natural voices from speakers or singers; pictures data are captured on hard surfaces: stones, wood, walls and paper; moving image data are viewed as actions. These analogue data can later be digitised by converting them to the desired digital formats. Born-digital data, on the other hand, are not just digital by conversion. They are generated as digital products from the outset. They occur in soft copies produced by software. Sound data occur as audio files (e.g. *.mp3*, *wav*, *.acc*, *.midi*, *.wma*); pictures and still images occur as image files (e.g. *.jpg*, *.png*, *.tif*, *.bmp*, *.gif*, *.svg*); moving images are created as video files (e.g. *.mp4*, *.mov*, *.avi*, *.wmv*); 3D objects are created in soft copies with the 3D perspective (e.g. *.fbx*, *.obj*, *.3ds*, *.skp*, *.stl*, *.blend*).

The study reveals a crucial problem that can hinder the on-going digitisation projects in the language. For a tone language like Yoruba which has a lot of minimal pairs and minimal sets where tones contrast, tone-marking problems can adversely affect comprehension. Where the context fails, digital texts often lack enough information to sustain comprehension where ambiguity surfaces from tone-marking neglects, a problem which humans may cope with in real life situations. It is therefore important to ensure tones are properly marked rather than depending on the context that is not digitally available. Due to the current rise in ICT, new language data on the web are usually born-digital. It is cheaper to type directly into word processor pages or web pages than to write on paper before scanning and digitising the script using OCR tools. This new drive for digital textual input is yet to be matched with the users competence in the orthography. The scope of this study is therefore limited to the role of tone in those Yoruba born-digital textual data.

Methodology

The study was conducted using the Yorùbá corpus called Yorùbá Web 2015 also known as *yorubawac15*. The corpus was accessed using Sketchengine's search on Yorùbá Web 2015 from <https://auth.sketchengine.eu/> (Kilgarriff, Baisa, Bušta, Jakubíček, Kovář, Michelfeit, Rychlý, & Suchomel, 2014). The data wrangling process in the study focuses on cleaning, structuring and preparing the raw unprocessed Yorùbá texts for proper tone-marking. The data were enriched with tone-marking to make them usable and meaningful.

The data used for the study were collected from 13 diverse websites. These are *wikipedia.org*, *gospelgo.com*, *alaroyeonline.com*, *nairaland.com*, *olayemioniroyin.com*,

slideshare.net, blogspot.cz, anti-el7ad.com, vegetable-gardens.biz, tripod.com, loveandtips.com, loveandtips.com, and themediaonline.co.za. They are selected with the following conditions: first, they are digitised Yorùbá texts; second, they have not been properly edited for thorough tone-marking. The data cleaning operation was done manually by reading through the lines of concordance to remove unnecessary duplicates and making the data representational of its source. Data analysis was planned to uncover patterns, themes, and insights recoverable from within the Yorùbá textual data on the selected websites.

Aja was selected because it is a common Yoruba word that can display tonal minimal pairs. It is preferred to other sets like *igba* and *ila*, which have been widely used in Yoruba tone illustrations. If these ones were used, most of the data mined will be from language learning corpora, and they will be too narrow to demonstrate the problem the study wanted to solve.

The data wrangling process includes selecting the right term to investigate in the corpora through concordancing, cleaning the data through deduplication, structuring the data sources and contextual relations, and preparing the raw data for analysis through proper tone-marking. Due to these processes, only 50 lines of the concordance were available for analysis in the study. Inconsistency in tone marking across Yorùbá websites can be problematic when such websites form part of a corpus.

Data

The data in the study comprises several websites from which the toneless word: *aja* was put in concordance from the websites. The concordance is provided in table 1 below.

N	Left	wic	Right	
	Kebu, Animere. Gbe :- Lábé èyí ni a ti rí: Ewe ati Gen/	ja	, Fon-Phla-Phera BENUE CONGO	Adja
	Suru, Yauri, Zuru. KOGI Kogi Adavi,	ja	okuta, Ankpa, bassa, Dekina, Ibaji, Idah,	Ajaoku ta
	lati ko lo si Abomey, larin won ni a ti ri	ja	, awon omo eya Gbe ti awon akotan nigbagbo pe	Adja

	ni won se idasile ilu na. Ibasepo larin awon eya	ja	ati eya Fon to fa idasile eya titun ti a mo si "Dah	Adja
	agbegbe Abomey ni Arin Gusu; ati Mina, Xueda, ati	ja	(ti won wa lati Togo) ni ekun odo. Fon ni	Adja
	o n so ede Fon, Yoruba tele won pelu 1.2 legbegberun,	ja	(600,000), Bariba (460,000), Ayizo (330,000), the	Adja
	eya eniyan 99% je awon omo Afrika (Yoruba, Fon,	ja	, Bariba at.bb.lo), awon omo Europe ko ju 10,000	Adja
	to gajulo laye pelu igasoke 4,900 m, won n pe bi	ja	aye. Himalaya Àsiá ilẹ Índià je asia orile-edede	loft
	ati Ebali, Sefo, ati Onamu. 24 Wonyi si li awon omo Sibeoni; ati	ja	on Ana: eyi ni Ana ti o ri awon isun omi gbigbona ni ijù, bi o ti mbó awon ketekete Sibeoni baba	Ajah Gen.36: 24
0	o si se arewa enia. 43 Filistini na si wi fun Dafidi pe, Emi ha nse	ja	bi, ti iwọ fi mu opá tò mi wá? Filistini na si fi Dafidi re nipa awon olorun re.	dog
1	re. 14 Nitori tani o ba Israeli fi jade? tani iwọ nlepa? Okú	ja	, tabi esinshin? 15 Ki Oluwa ki o se onidajo, ki o si dajo larin emi ati	dog
2	nitori orọ wonyi ti Işboşeti so fun u, o si wipe, Emi ise ori	ja	bi? emi ti mo mba Juda ja, ti mo si şanu loni fun idile Saulu baba re,	dog
3	teriba, o si wipe, Kini iranşe re jasi, ti iwọ o fi ma wo okú	ja	bi emi? 9 Oba si pe Siba iranşe Saulu, o si wi fun u pe, Gbogbo	dog

4	won. 13 Hasaeli si wipe, Sugbon kinla? Iranşe reşe	ja	, ti yio fi şe nkan nla yi? Elişa si dahùn wipe, Oluwa ti fi hàn mi pe,	dog
5	omọ Nebati, ati bi ile Baasa omọ Ahijah; 10 Awon	ja	yio si je Jesebeli ni oko Jesreeli, ki yio si eniti yio sinku re. O si si	dog
6	owọ Elijah iranşe re ara Tişbi wipe, Ni oko Jesreeli li awon	ja	yio je eran-ara Jesebeli: 37 Oku Jesebeli yio si dabi imi ni igbe, ni	dog
7	li erere; iwọ o mu mi dubule ninu erupe iku. 16 Nitoriti awon	ja	yi mi ka: ijo awon enia buburu ti ka mi mo: nwon lu mi li owọ, nwon si lu mi li eshe. 17 Mo le ka	dog
8	lowo. 20 Gba okan mi lowo ida; eni mi kanna lowo agbara	ja	ni. 21 Gba mi kuro li enu kiniun ni; ki iwọ ki o si gbohun mi lati ibi	dog
9	nwon ndubule, nwon fe ma togbе. 11 Nitoto ojeun	ja	ni nwon ti ki iyó, ati olusó agutan ti ko moye ni nwon:	dog
0	23 Ki eshe re ki o le pon ninu eje awon ota re, ati ahon awon	ja	re ninu re na. 24 Nwon ti ri irin re, Olorun; ani irin Olorun mi, Oba	dog
1	asiwere si ishe, ti o si gba awon olurekoja si ishe-owo. 11 Bi	ja	ti ipada sinu ebi re, beli asiwere itun pada sinu were re.	dog
2	fun awon eeyan re, sugbon kokoro kan wa nibe to ba eyin	ja	je. ... Ija n bo! Awon gomina ko fee sanwo osu tuntun mo o	dog

3	Okan ninu awon ohun ti Yoruba n pe ni a-teyinrogbon ree o. A-teyinrogbon, a ge eti	ja	, o wa n loo fi obe pamo, se iyen tun ran oro re ni. Jonathan yoo tun fowo	dog
4	bi nnkan se n lo ninu egbe oselu ACN ipinle Ondo bayii, o see se ki ija ajadiju, ija	ja	pin yeleyele sele ninu egbe naa laipe nitori bi opo awon omo egbe naa se n mura lati di gomina lodun	à-jà: nom-fight
5	Nibo leyin n gbe, Nibo leyin wa O doluwooro jin wooro, o doluwooro jin wooro, oku	ja	ki i gbo, oku agbo ki i kan... Bi Haruna isola se mo orin i ko to, ti okiki re si gbale kankan, kinni kan	dog
6	ni kan to mo-on-moran ara e lo sorun apapandodo laduugbo Idi-Oro	ja	to ba fee sonu, ko ni i gbo fere olode Mo ti soro yii leekan o, sugbon n ko so o ni ekun-un-re	dog
7	Ile n jeeyan, awon eni nla ti re koja lo Akintola lo si Kano o bo,	ja	to rele ekun to bo ni, ba a ba ki aja ku ewu, ka si ki ekun naa pe o ku ewu	dog
8	awon to je olugbe adugbo kan ti won n pe ni Peace land, ... Read More Alabi to ji	ja	alaja gbe ateni to ta a fun n'Iganmu ti dero ile-ejo Leyin to gbe aja meta to je ti Ogbeni	dog
9	a mi o, oko mi ti gba ile ti mo fowo mi ra Ojukwu n sepade, Obasanjo naa n sepade, a fi bii	ja	to ri ikooko to n gbo, ninu aja pelu ikooko, eni kan naa lesu yoo se Ni asiko ti awon omo-ogun Biafra	dog
0	ti mi o mobi ti mo wa, ti mi o si mo ohun ti mo n se rara	ja	to ba rele ekun to bo, keeyan maa ki i ku ewu ni, bee gege loro omo	dog

1	E mura si i daadaa Eepa n pa ara re, o ni oun n pa	ja	. Awon ti won n pese telifoonu fun gbog	Dog
2	ko e l'obe je tan So fun bobo Ifeleke yen pe ere ti	ja	ba f'ogun odun sa, ko ni gba esin ni ojo kan.	Dog
3	padanu eto re ni ile Nairaland. Mo lero wipe bi	ja	ba n siwin o ye ki o mo oju olowo re o. Abata loro eleyi	Dog
4	Ma se be mo oooo, is not good at all.	ja	la jenu iwo omugo yi, kete kete le si ri, kata kata nbo lona,	Dog
5	Sebi awon agba loni ilu ki i wa laini oba alade. Leyin ti Oba Adebiyi Adesida goke	ja	, awon afobaje ilu Akure ti pe birikoto lati fi Omooba 'birin Adetutu Adesida Ojei to je beere	Loft
6	Sebi awon Yoruba loni, are-maja kan ko si,	ja	-ma-pari-e lo buru jojo. Bi o tile je wi pe iyapa D'banj ati Don	a-jà: nom-fight
7	si lule eleyii to mu ki koto ti won wa ni inu re ja sinu	ja	ile sohun raurau. Kelly Hansome ti gbe orin jade lati fi	cavity, hole
8	ko le gbagbo wipe Jesu le sami awon Keferi bi	ja	ati eledede ati ki o si ma ba iya re soro pe Obirin yi,	dog
9	olori- buruku.” Matheu 7:6: “E mase fi ohun mimo fun	ja	, ki e ma si se so peril nyin siwaju eledede...”	dog
0	ohun ti a maa n bukaata sinu re, tori naasanma ni	ja	re ti a gbega lori re, ati pe ile ni ibusun atiite ati	loft

1	ee lo, a gbo pe leyin ti o pa Lekham tan o gun oke o si wo inu	ja	ile lo. Ibeere niyi: Ti o ba je pe moleka / angeeli lo pa Lekham bi Ahmadi se fe ki a gbagbo,	depth
2	oro etan tikarare. A gba itoni emi ati iru omoleyin, ti o buru ju	ja	ati igbe aye aimo awon maa so asotele nile, ati wipe pelu owo ara won ati pelu ogbon alumo-koroyi	dog
3	itijú bo Àjàpá.	JA	ILE NI ABEOKUTA Olorun ti se tan lati gbe ija awa omo naijiria	cavity
4	mu ki o baa le ya ooru ni ile re. Inu	ja	naa dun lati kuro ninu iji. Ni ale ojo naa, ile gba ina.	dog
5	mimu iderun ba awon omo ile Naijiria 2. gbigbe ogun	ja	aiwehin ti iwa ibaje 3. sise ajinde igbagbo	dog
6	mehe pupo ni agbegbe wa nibi Ogbontagi	ja	-fun-eto omoniyani kan, Ogbeni (Komureedi) Mashood Erubami	a-jà: NOM-fighter “activist”
7	Ni ibere lati oririn ara je ti o ni inira Oniwura, ewure, awon	ja	di aso ti awo-ara, o dara fun awon manufacture ti yangan alawo	dog
8	Ninu awon etutu ti won ma nfi sami si odun naa ni ki won pa	ja	ati Agbo. Odokunrin ati odobinrin ti won tagun yoo da eje won si ara, leyin naa won yoo wa fi	dog
9	Boya wa ti je eya atijo-asa yinyin ipara firisa ninu re oke	ja	. O le je Fun lati gba die ninu awon yinyi	loft

0	o ba ohun ini nipase re ebi . 201 . O ti je nipase awon	ja	, jackals , wolves ati aran, Crows ati hawks ju je	dog
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Table 1. "Aja" in yorubawac15 corpus concordance

Discussion of the analysis

Many of the born-digital Yorùbá textual data are rendered in forms that violate the standard orthography, especially in tone-marking. In table 2, Olumuyiwa (2013:47) cites how Abẹ̀òkúta community web page violated tone-marking amidst other orthography violations.

Web form	Clean form	gloss
E kaaro-ro	ẹ kááárọ̀	good morning
n Okuuri	n ọ̀kùnrì	male
Obirin	obìnrin	female
Bee ni	bẹ́ ẹ̀ ni	yes
Odaa	ó dáa	it is good
Ejo	ẹ̀ jọ̀ ọ́	please
Se e ni?	şé ẹ̀ ni?	do you have?
E se	Ẹ̀ şé	thank you
Ta-ni?	Ta ni?	Who is it

Kí-ni?	Kí ni	what is it
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Table 2. Orthography cleaning (adapted from Olumuyiwa, 2013:47)

The concordance in table 1 is compressed to align with the source website in Figure 1. There are 13 sources. The frequency of the keyword-in-context is placed after each of the websites. *wikipedia.org* has 8 mentions (concordance lines: 1-8) The highest occurrence of the KWIC is in *gospelgo.com* with 13 mentions (concordance lines: 22-31). At *alaroyeonline.com*, there are 10 mentions (concordance lines: 9-21). *Nairaland.com*, *olayemioniroyin.com* and *slideshare.net* have 3 mentions each. *Blogspot.cz*, *anti-el7ad.com* and *vegetable-gardens.biz* have 3 mentions each. *tripod.com*, *loveandtips.com*, *loveandtips.com*, and *thediaonline.co.za* have a mention each.

Figure 1. Distribution of “aja” per listed website

The concordance entries are categorised by their sources respectively in Figure 1. The first group comprises data from *Wikipedia* documents. The second group is from a religious website with the domain name: *gospelgo.com*. The third group is the online edition of the Yorùbá newspaper, *Alaroye*, available at *alaroyeonline.com*. Data from *Nairaland*, a very popular Nigerian social website, comes next. In short, the grouping follows the order in which the sources are listed above.

This study used *aja* as the *key word in context* (kwic) to construct the concordance. *Aja* output of the 50-line concordance has the following outcomes: *ajá* “dog” (31 times); *àjà* “loft/cavity” (9 times); *Adja* “a people” (6 times); *A-jà a-* NOM+VP (4 times); *Ajah* “name in the bible” (1 time); and *Aja-* as part of *Ajaokuta* (1 time).

Figure 2. Presentation of the data cleaning on “aja” *raw data; () cleaned data.

With the tone clearly marked, the words have their tags interpretable even without formal lemmatisation. The most frequent item is *ajá* “dog”; it occurs 31 times. Next to this is *àjà* “loft/roof/hole” which occurs 9 times. There are two cases where *aja* came from non-Nigerian languages as in Figure 2. The first is *Adja* written as *Aja* in the Yorùbá textual source where the crawler mined it. The word represents an ethnic group in Benin and Togo Republics. The second one is *Ajah*, also written as *Aja* in its source document, the Yorùbá bible. This is a Hebrew name found in Yorùbá version of the bible in Genesis 36: 24. Both words are pronounced with their first syllables stressed. This could have been rendered in Yorùbá with a high tone on the stressed syllable as reproduced in Table 3.

N	raw form	clean form from the source	Clean form for Yorùbá	gloss
	aja	Ajah	Ájà	“a people”
	aja	Aja	Ájà	name in the bible

Table 3. Presentation of the data cleaning on “aja” for “Adja” and “Ajah”

Having the data in Table 3 bearing the high tone on the first syllable clearly shows that those items are not Yorùbá words. The clue provided through the high tone mark is enough to show they are borrowed.

Another issue of ambiguity caused by poor tone marking results in the possibly mistaking the bound morpheme, *A-jà*, for the free morpheme, *aja*. *A-jà* forms part of a verbal noun which is derived by combining the nominalising prefix *a-* with the verb *jà* “fight”. The three cases are analysed in Table 4.

N	OM prefix	STEM with clean Yorùbá data	Gloss
	-	jà pín yéleyèlẹ fight split scatter-about	“a fight that breaks into several factions and fronts”
	-	jà-fún-ẹ̀tọ̀ ọ̀mọ̀niyàn fight-for-right-human’s	“human right activist”
	-	jà-má-parí-ẹ̀ fight-NOT-finish-it	“a monger of unendless strife”

Table 4. Presentation of the data cleaning on aja for “àjà pín yéleyèlẹ”, “ajà-fún-ẹ̀tọ̀ ọ̀mọ̀niyàn” and “ajà-má-parí-ẹ̀”.

In Table 4, there are two types of nominalisation prefixes. The first one has a low-toned prefix (marked with a grave accent). This prefix carries thematic imports. It simply assigns a name to the action of the verb (See the first item in Table 4). The second and the third item in Table 4 have the mid-toned agentive nominalisation prefix. Mid-tone is unmarked in Yorùbá texts. The tone mark information on the nominalisation prefixes is part of grammar. Disregarding such vital rules of the grammar will make digitised Yorùbá texts difficult for accurate digitisation projects.

Discussion of the findings

The study has revealed the importance of tone marking in digitised Yorùbá texts. Due to poor use of tone diacritics on large data sets of digitised Yorùbá texts, it has become difficult to have good results with properly tone-marked Yorùbá texts while using search engines on the web (Asubiaro, 2014). The search engines are simply confused when the tone-marked search words do not match the desired results because of their incompatibility in form due to unmatching tone diacritics.

Rather than dwelling on the problem caused by neglect of tone marks on Yorùbá digitised text, more efforts have been placed on the solution to restore tone in the language (Asahiah, 2014;

Asahiah, Odejobi, and Adagunodo, 2017). This study provides two main patterns for general users of the language in providing born-digital textual data that will contribute to the ongoing digitisation of the language. The first option is the use of unicode Yorùbá keyboard. The second option is the use of predictive tone-marking input tools. The predictive input tools differ from the typical input keyboards, because it offers language users the opportunity to make the right choice from a list of options by merely clicking on it.

Yorùbá unicode keyboard applications: There are several keyboards software that can be installed on the personal computer which can be used to type Yorùbá tones. Ajao, Babatunde, Asapetu and Yusuf's (2020) Yorùbá Character Keyboard proposes a combination of ASCII and Unicode to generate unicode for Yorùbá characters with tone marks and subdot diacritics. See screenshot in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Tone-marking approach in Yorùbá character keyboard by reading tone mark and letter as a single character on the keyboard

The goal of this Yorùbá Character Keyboard is to generate a single code point for Yorùbá characters instead of combining two or more keys on the keyboard to type a single character. The

keyboard is so detailed that users can type the high-toned vowel *á* and the low-toned vowel *à* from different keys labeled after them. A combination of different keys is not required. Availability and the use of input tools like this will reduce tone-marking problem in Yorùbá born-digital textual data sets.

Predictive applications: Some predictive applications are also available. Users just type the words in plain Latin letters, then some tone-marked options will appear from which the intended word can be selected (Adewuyi, 2017; Adebara and Adelani, 2022).

Figure 4. Typing in the toneless Yorùbá data “Yoruba dun” into the input box.

Figure 5. Tone-marking the first syllable “yo” by clicking on the right option “Yo”.

Figure 6. Tone-marking the second syllable “ru” by clicking on the right option “ru”.

Figure 7. Tone-marking the third syllable “ba” by clicking on the right option “bá”

Figure 8. Tone-marking the second word “dun” by clicking on the right option “dùn”.

Adebara and Adelani’s (2022) tone-marking software provides a word-length tone-marking application in similar way choosing from available options provided for the writer.

Conclusion

While improper tone-marking is generally seen as abnormal in Yorùbá orthography, its use in digital texts has a greater consequence. It can confuse digital textual processing tools in their analyses as it does in the use of *Sketch Engine's* corpora and concordance compilation in the current study. Erroneous judgments coming from tone-marking can lead to false outputs in various analyses making use of such digital tools. Improper tone-marking can also hinder the ongoing, as well as future, digitisation projects in Yorùbá. Thus, proper tone-marking is crucial to digital humanities projects in Yorùbá. awareness on the proper use of Yoruba tones in the digital space should therefore be encouraged. Software developers should carry along Yorùbá digital content creators on their current developments of various input software that can aid their efficiency. Linguists should also be considering necessary revisions in the tone orthography that will ensure born-digital data sets are properly codified to reflect the norm in the orthography. Automation of predictive typing of tone marks should be a way to go; this will reduce the time spent in typing Yorùbá texts and the mental load facing textual input of Yorùbá born-digital data.

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